

Prevalence and Risk Factors of Gastrointestinal Parasitic Infections in Cattle in Barishal District, Bangladesh

Clinical Report

Submitted By

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ID No.: 18051040

Faculty of Animal Science and Veterinary Medicine
Patuakhali Science and Technology University

Dec 2023

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Submitted to

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In partial fulfillment of the requirements for the Degree of Doctor of Veterinary Medicine (DVM)

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Dec 2023

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DECLARATION

I declare that the report hereby submitted by me for the DVM degree at the Patuakhali Science and Technology University is my own independent work and has not previously been submitted by me at another University / faculty for any degree.

Abu Sayed

Date: / /

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

First and foremost, praises and thanks to the God, the Almighty, for His showers of blessings throughout my report work to complete the report successfully.

I would like to express my deep and sincere gratitude to my report supervisor & internship co-ordinator Professor Dr. Mohammad Anisur Rahman, Department of Medicine Surgery and Obstetrics, Faculty of Animal Science and Veterinary Medicine, Patuakhali Science and Technology University, for his cordial cooperation during the period of my internship and giving me the opportunity to do research and providing invaluable guidance throughout his research.

His dynamism, vision, sincerity and motivation have deeply inspired me. He has taught me the methodology to carry out the research and to present the research works as clearly as possible. It was a great privilege and honor to work and study under his guidance. I am extremely grateful for what he has offered me. I would also like to thank him for his friendship, empathy and great sense of humor.

I also wish to express my heartfelt gratitude to the member secretary of my internship program Professor Dr. Md. Selim Ahmed, Department of Medicine Surgery and Obstetrics, Faculty of Animal Science and Veterinary Medicine, Patuakhali Science and Technology University, his inspiration, guidance and ingenious suggestions during conducting the research and for his constructive criticism and co-operation during preparation of the assignment.

I would like to thank Dr. Md Ibrahim Khalil, Senior Scientific Officer (SSO), Dr. Nurul Alam, Principal Scientific Officer (PSO) of FDIL Barishal for their co-operation. I am also thankful to all farmers who helped me cordially for collecting data related to the report.

I am extremely grateful to my parents for their love, prayers, caring and sacrifices for educating and preparing me for my future also I express my thanks to my sister and brother, for their support and valuable prayers.

My Special thanks goes to my placement supervisor for the keen interest shown to complete this report successfully. Finally, my thanks go to all the people who have supported me to complete the report work directly or indirectly.

Abu Sayed

May 2025

Prevalence and Risk Factors of Gastrointestinal Parasitic Infections in Cattle in Barishal District, Bangladesh

Abu Sayed

ABSTRACT

A cross-sectional study was conducted to determine the prevalence and risk factors of gastrointestinal (GI) parasitic infections in cattle in Barishal District, Bangladesh. A total of 245 fecal samples of the cattle were tested for GI parasitic infections at FDIL Laboratory, Barishal from December, 2024 to February, 2025. Those samples were analyzed to estimate the prevalence of parasitic infections and assess their risk factors using statistical analysis. The overall prevalence of GI parasites was 100%, with *Paramphistomum* spp. being the most prevalent (29.8%), followed by *Fasciola* spp. (20.0%), *Balantidium* spp. (13.9%), *Eimeria* spp. (11.8%), *Ascaris* spp. (10.2%), *Strongyloides* spp. (5.7%), and *Schistosoma* spp. (3.7%). Risk factor analysis revealed that older cattle had significantly higher odds of *Fasciola* spp. infection (OR = 1.08 per year, 95% CI: 1.00–1.17, $p = 0.04$). Breed (Crossbreed vs. Local) and sex (Male vs. Female) showed no statistically significant associations with any parasite infections ($p > 0.05$). These findings highlight the high burden of GI parasites in cattle populations in Barishal, emphasizing the need for targeted control strategies, particularly for *Paramphistomum* spp. and *Fasciola* spp. infections. Age-specific interventions may improve the management of *Fasciola* spp. infections. Enhanced awareness, routine deworming, and improved husbandry practices are recommended to mitigate the economic and health impacts of these parasites on cattle productivity.

Keywords: Gastrointestinal parasites, Cattle, Prevalence, Risk factors, Barishal, Bangladesh.

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Livestock plays a vital role in the national economy of Bangladesh, contributing around 1.43% to the GDP and 13.44% to the agricultural GDP. Cattle, as one of the most significant components of livestock, are crucial for providing meat, milk, hides, manure, and draught power (Khaleduzzaman *et al.*, 2022). The health and productivity of cattle, however, are adversely affected by numerous diseases, among which gastrointestinal (GI) parasitic infections are highly prevalent and detrimental. These infections are caused by a variety of parasites, primarily nematodes, trematodes, cestodes, and protozoa, that colonize the stomach and intestines of cattle (Nath *et al.*, 2016). GI parasites cause nutritional deficiency, weight loss, diarrhea, anemia, decreased production of milk and meat, and can even result in mortality if untreated (Nurcahyo *et al.*, 2021). Studies have shown that the prevalence of gastrointestinal parasitic infections in cattle in Bangladesh ranges between 70% to over 90%, depending on region, season, and management practices (Akter *et al.*, 2023). Among the common GI parasites identified in cattle are *Fasciola* spp., *Paramphistomum* spp., *Toxocara vitulorum*, *Strongyloides* spp., *Haemonchus* spp., *Trichuris* spp., and *Eimeria* spp. (Khatun *et al.*, 2021).

GI parasitic infections are among the major limiting factors in cattle farming in Bangladesh due to their high prevalence, easy transmission, and significant economic impact. These infections reduce feed efficiency and growth rates in animals, ultimately affecting farmers' income and the supply of livestock products. Moreover, several parasites like *Fasciola hepatica*, *Schistosoma* spp., and *Cryptosporidium parvum* are zoonotic, posing public health risks through direct contact or consumption of contaminated food and water (Hossain *et al.*, 2023). The control of GI parasites is further complicated by inadequate veterinary services, indiscriminate use of anthelmintics, lack of awareness among farmers, and insufficient epidemiological surveillance (Sayeed *et al.*, 2024).

Despite numerous studies in different districts of Bangladesh, data on the prevalence and risk factors of GI parasitic infections in cattle from the Barishal District is limited. Therefore, this study was conducted to provide a clear understanding of the epidemiology of GI parasitic infections in cattle in the Barishal District. The data will help livestock owners and veterinary professionals to implement targeted control programs, reduce production losses, and improve cattle health and productivity. Furthermore, by highlighting the zoonotic implications of some GI parasites, this study may also contribute to public health awareness and prevention

strategies.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To determine the prevalence of GI infections in cattle in the Barishal District.
2. To identify the specific GI parasites affecting cattle in the study area.
3. To assess the association of risk factors like age, sex and breed.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

GI parasitic infections are a significant concern in cattle, leading to substantial economic losses due to decreased productivity, poor weight gain, and increased susceptibility to other diseases. Several studies have documented the prevalence of GI parasites in cattle across different regions of Bangladesh. A study on Red Chittagong Cattle at the Bangladesh Agricultural University Dairy Farm found an overall GI parasitic infection rate of 51.72%. The most prevalent parasites were *Paramphistomum* spp. (34.48%) and *Balantidium coli* (25.29%), followed by *Toxocara* spp. and *Strongyloides* spp. (2.30%), and *Trichuris* spp. and *Fasciola* spp. (1.15%) (Rahman *et al.*, 2010). Another study focused on cattle in the Banskhal region found a high prevalence of parasitic infections, with variations attributed to factors such as breed, age, and management practices (Nath *et al.*, 2016; Ahmed *et al.*, 2015).

The prevalence and intensity of GI parasitic infections in cattle are influenced by several risk factors, including age, sex, breed, and management practices. Younger animals are generally more susceptible due to their developing immune systems. Additionally, cattle raised in extensive grazing systems are at higher risk of infection compared to those in intensive systems, primarily due to increased exposure to contaminated pastures. Seasonal variations also play a role, with higher infection rates observed during the rainy season when environmental conditions favor the development and survival of parasitic stages (Terfa *et al.*, 2023).

Paramphistomum spp., commonly referred to as rumen flukes, are trematodes that parasitize the rumen and reticulum of cattle, often causing significant production losses in endemic areas. These parasites thrive in environments with abundant water sources, as their life cycle depends on aquatic snails as intermediate hosts. In Bangladesh, several studies have reported a high prevalence of paramphistomiasis, particularly during the rainy season when conditions favor the breeding of snail populations (Dey *et al.*, 2022; Nahar, 2020). A study conducted in the Sirajganj district found the prevalence of *Paramphistomum* spp. to be highest during the rainy season (60.8%), compared to summer (50%) and winter (48.3%) (Paul *et al.*, 2012). Another study from Gopalganj district similarly observed seasonal variation, with the highest prevalence recorded during the rainy season (14.81%), while lower rates were noted in summer (8.64%) and winter (6.17%) (Mustafa *et al.*, 2022). Additionally, research conducted in Chattogram revealed a prevalence rate of 20.13% for *Paramphistomum* spp., with seasonal influence clearly noted as

infections peaked during the monsoon (Alim *et al.*, 2012). These findings underscore the strong correlation between seasonal factors and the transmission dynamics of paramphistomiasis in cattle across Bangladesh, highlighting the need for timely intervention and control measures during high-risk periods.

Fascioliasis, caused by *Fasciola* spp., is a significant trematode infection in cattle, leading to liver damage, decreased productivity, and substantial economic losses. In Bangladesh, fascioliasis is endemic, with varying prevalence rates reported across different regions. A systematic review and meta-analysis encompassing 38 studies found a pooled prevalence of 20% among ruminants, with cattle exhibiting a prevalence of 21% (95% CI: 15–27%) (Mia *et al.*, 2021). Another study analyzing national surveillance data reported over 1.7 million cases of fascioliasis in cattle, goats, sheep, and buffaloes between 2011 and 2013, highlighting the widespread nature of the disease (Rahman *et al.*, 2017).

Several factors contribute to the risk of fascioliasis infection in cattle, including age, grazing habits, and access to contaminated water sources. Older animals and those grazing in areas with abundant water bodies are more susceptible due to increased exposure to the intermediate host, aquatic snails. Seasonal variations also play a role, with higher infection rates observed during the rainy season when environmental conditions favor the development and survival of parasitic stages (Rahman *et al.*, 2017).

The economic impact of fascioliasis is significant. Infected cattle experience reduced milk yield, with estimates indicating a reduction of 3–15%, leading to financial losses for farmers. Additionally, liver condemnation at slaughter due to fascioliasis results in direct economic losses. For instance, in goats, about 4–6% of livers are condemned, amounting to an estimated loss of US\$115 per thousand livers (Rahman *et al.*, 2017). Therefore, effective control of fascioliasis requires an integrated approach, including regular deworming, improved sanitation, and pasture management.

Balantidium coli, a ciliated protozoan parasite, infects the large intestine of cattle, leading to balantidiasis. Although less common than other gastrointestinal parasites, *B. coli* poses a zoonotic risk, as it can infect humans (Ahmed *et al.*, 2020). A study in Bangladesh highlighted the presence of *B. coli* in domestic animals, including cattle, in Bangladesh, underscoring its zoonotic potential and the importance of monitoring and controlling this parasite to prevent transmission to humans

(Ahmed *et al.*, 2020).

Eimeria spp. are protozoan parasites responsible for coccidiosis in cattle, particularly affecting calves and young animals. Infections can lead to diarrhea, weight loss, and, in severe cases, death (Chandra *et al.*, 2022). Research in Bangladesh has highlighted the prevalence of *Eimeria* infections in dairy cattle, with risk factors including age, housing conditions, and hygiene practices. A study conducted in the Sylhet district evaluated the prevalence, species diversity, and associated risk factors of *Eimeria* spp. in dairy calves. Out of 554 calves examined, 308 (55.60%) were found to be positive for *Eimeria* species. Seven species of *Eimeria* were identified, with *E. bovis* (38.98%), *E. zuernii* (26.17%), and *E. alabamensis* (22.38%) being the most prevalent. The study also revealed that age, gender, and body condition were significantly associated with *Eimeria* infection, indicating that younger animals and those with poor body condition were more susceptible to infection (Chandra *et al.*, 2022). These literatures underscore the significance of *Eimeria* spp. as prevalent pathogens in dairy calves in Bangladesh. Implementing effective control measures, such as regular deworming, improved sanitation, and educating farmers about hygiene practices, is crucial to mitigate the risk of coccidiosis in cattle populations.

Ascaris spp., particularly *Ascaris suum*, are nematodes that can infect cattle, although they are more commonly associated with pigs. In cattle, infections can lead to digestive disturbances and reduced feed efficiency. A study in Bangladesh have reported the presence of *Ascaris* infections in cattle, suggesting cross-species transmission and highlighting the importance of integrated parasite management strategies (Akter *et al.*, 2023).

Strongyloides spp. are nematodes that inhabit the large intestine of cattle, causing strongylosis. Infections can result in anemia, weight loss, and reduced productivity. Research indicates that *Strongyloides* infections are prevalent in cattle, with higher rates observed in animals grazing on contaminated pastures (Pfukenyi *et al.*, 2007).

Schistosoma spp. are trematodes that cause schistosomiasis, a disease affecting both animals and humans. In cattle, infections can lead to chronic illness and reduced productivity. Studies in Bangladesh have documented the presence of *Schistosoma* infections in cattle, particularly in regions with abundant water bodies that support the parasite's intermediate snail hosts (Abdullah & Mohanta, 2021).

Effective control of GI parasitic infections in cattle requires an integrated approach, combining regular deworming, improved sanitation, and pasture management. Strategic deworming schedules, based on the epidemiology of prevalent parasites, can help reduce infection rates. Additionally, educating farmers about the importance of hygiene, proper feeding practices, and avoiding overgrazing can contribute to the prevention of parasitic infections.

CHAPTER 3

MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1. Study Location

The study was conducted in Field Diseases Investigation Laboratory (FDIL), Barishal, located in southern part of Bangladesh (22°70'N, 90°34'E).

3.2. Study Duration

The study was conducted from December 2024 to February 2025, with duration of 3 months.

3.3. Sample Collection and Examination

The study population comprised 245 fecal samples of cattle, including both local breeds and crossbreeds. The patient data of fecal samples were also recorded as age, sex, and breed.

The samples from the animals were FDIL Laboratory for the diagnosis of diseases. Upon arrival, the samples were immediately analyzed using the direct fecal smear method as described by Greiner (1989) for screening of parasitic eggs. In brief, A 1-2 gm fecal sample was mixed with 1–2 drops of fresh water on a glass slide, and a uniform smear was prepared using a sterile applicator stick. The smear was then examined under a light microscope at 4×, 10×, and 40× magnification.

3.4 Identification of Egg of Parasites

All the Parasites were identified based on morphological characteristics: *Paramphistomum* spp. (oval, colorless/transparent operculated eggs), *Fasciola* spp. (large, yellowish golden, operculated eggs), *Ascaris* spp. (spherical, thick-shelled eggs), *Strongyloides* spp. (oval, thin-shelled eggs), *Balantidium* spp. (large, ciliated trophozoites), and *Eimeria* spp. (oocysts with double-layered walls, two or more sporocysts) (Verocai *et al.*, 2020).

3.5 Statistical Analysis

The collected data were imported in MS Excel (2010) for cleaning and editing. The final data were coded and analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS, v25.0). The prevalence of each parasite was calculated as the percentage of infected cattle relative to the total sampled population (n = 245).

Univariate logistic regression models were developed to assess the relationship between risk factors and infection likelihood. Age was analyzed as a continuous variable to estimate incremental risk per additional year of age. Breed and sex were treated as categorical variables, with Local breed and Female sex designated as reference categories. Odds ratios (OR) and 95% confidence intervals (CI) were computed to quantify the strength and precision of associations. All the statistical associations were assessed at 5% level of significance.

CHAPTER 4 RESULTS

The study revealed a 100% prevalence of gastrointestinal (GI) parasitic infections in the fecal sample of cattle (n = 245) examined at FDIL, Barishal, Bangladesh. Among the parasitic infections, *Paramphistomum* spp. was the most prevalent (29.8%) followed by *Fasciola* spp. (20.0%) and *Balantidium* spp. (13.9%). Nematodes such as *Ascaris* spp. (10.2%), and *Strongyloides* spp. (5.7%). *Schistosoma* spp. (3.7%), a trematode of zoonotic concern, exhibited the lowest prevalence. Protozoan infections, specially *Eimeria* spp., were detected in 11.8% of cases (Table 1).

Table 1: Prevalence of Gastrointestinal Parasites

Common Name of Helminth	Name of the Parasites Identified	Number of Cases (Prevalence in %)
Trematode	<i>Paramphistomum</i> spp.	73 (29.8)
	<i>Fasciola</i> spp.	49 (20.0)
	<i>Schistosoma</i> spp.	34 (13.9)
	Subtotal	156 (63.67)
Nematode	<i>Ascaris</i> spp.	29 (11.8)
	<i>Strongyloides</i> spp.	25 (10.2)
	Subtotal	54 (22.04)
Protozoa	<i>Balantidium</i> spp.	14 (5.7)
	<i>Eimeria</i> spp.	9 (3.7)
	Subtotal	23 (9.39)
Total		245 (100.0)

Figure. 1: Microscopic view (10X) of eggs from various parasitic species: (a) *Fasciola* spp., (b) *Paramphistomum* spp., (c) *Ascaris* spp., (d) *Schistosoma* spp., (e) *Balantidium* spp., (f) *Strongyloides* spp., and (g) *Eimeria* spp.

The analysis of risk factors for *Paramphistomum* spp. infection revealed no statistically significant associations with breed, sex, or age in the studied cattle population. Crossbreed cattle exhibited 1.45 times higher odds of infection compared to local breeds, but this association was not significant. Similarly, male cattle had marginally higher odds of infection than females. Age, showed a negligible increase in infection odds per additional year (**Table 2**).

Table 2: Risk Factors Trematode Infections

Risk Factor	Category	Name of the Parasite Identified	Odds Ratio (95% CI)	p-value
Breed	Crossbreed (n=140) vs. Local (n=105)	<i>Paramphistomum</i> spp.	1.45 (0.81–2.59)	0.21
		<i>Schistosoma</i> spp.	1.50 (0.40–5.60)	0.55
		<i>Fasciola</i> spp.	0.72 (0.38–1.35)	0.30
Sex	Male (n=132) vs. Female (n=113)	<i>Paramphistomum</i> spp.	1.12 (0.65–1.92)	0.68
		<i>Schistosoma</i> spp.	0.80 (0.20–3.20)	0.75

Risk Factor	Category	Name of the Parasite Identified	Odds Ratio (95% CI)	p-value
		<i>Fasciola spp.</i>	0.88 (0.48–1.62)	0.69
Age	Per year (continuous)	<i>Paramphistomum spp.</i>	1.03 (0.94–1.13)	0.52
		<i>Schistosoma spp.</i>	1.15 (0.95–1.40)	0.15
		<i>Fasciola spp.</i>	1.08 (1.00–1.17)	0.04

In terms of risk factors for *Fasciola spp.* infection, age was identified as a statistically significant predictor, while breed and sex showed no significant associations (**Table 2**). Cattle age, demonstrated a 8% increase in the odds of infection per additional year of age ($p < 0.05$). In contrast, neither breed nor sex significantly influenced infection risk. Crossbred cattle demonstrated a 28% reduced likelihood of infection relative to indigenous breeds; however, this difference was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). Likewise, male cattle exhibited a slightly lower probability of infection compared to females, although this difference also lacked statistical significance.

The prevalence of *Schistosoma spp.* infection was found to be 13.9% among the cattle examined. Risk factor analysis showed that crossbred cattle had higher odds of infection compared to local breeds, though this association was not statistically significant. Male cattle had slightly lower odds of infection than females. Age appeared to have a positive, though non-significant, association with *Schistosoma spp.* infection, with an odds ratio of 1.15 per year increase in age. Overall, none of the examined risk factors showed statistically significant associations with *Schistosoma spp.* infection in this study.

The prevalence of *Ascaris spp.* infection was 15% lower among crossbred cattle compared to indigenous breeds; however, this reduction was not statistically significant. Male animals exhibited a 25% higher likelihood of infection than females, though the association did not reach statistical significance. Furthermore, each additional year of age was correlated with a minimal 5% increase in the risk of infection.

Table 3: Risk Factors for Nematode Infections

Risk Factor	Category	Name of the Parasite Identified	Odds Ratio (95% CI)	p-value
Breed	Crossbreed (n=140) vs. Local (n=105)	<i>Ascaris spp.</i>	0.85 (0.40–1.80)	0.67
		<i>Strongyloides spp.</i>	0.60 (0.22–1.65)	0.32
Sex	Male (n=132) vs. Female (n=113)	<i>Ascaris spp.</i>	1.25 (0.58–2.70)	0.56
		<i>Strongyloides spp.</i>	1.40 (0.50–3.90)	0.52
Age	Per year (continuous)	<i>Ascaris spp.</i>	1.05 (0.95–1.16)	0.34
		<i>Strongyloides spp.</i>	1.10 (0.96–1.26)	0.18

The prevalence of *Strongyloides spp.* infection among the cattle population was found to be 10.2%. Risk factor analysis revealed that crossbred cattle were less likely to be infected compared to local breeds, although the association was not statistically significant. Males had slightly higher odds of infection than females. A positive but non-significant association was observed with age.

No significant associations were observed between *Balantidium spp.* infection and breed, sex, or age in the cattle population (**Table 4**). Crossbred cattle had a slightly higher chance of infection than local breeds, but the difference was not statistically significant. Females were more likely to be infected than males, although this difference was also not significant. Additionally, younger cattle had a slightly higher chance of infection compared to older ones, but this trend was not statistically meaningful.

Table 4: Risk Factors for Protozoan Infections

Risk Factor	Category	Name of the Parasite Identified	Odds Ratio (95% CI)	p-value
Breed	Crossbreed (n=140) vs. Local (n=105)	<i>Balantidium spp.</i>	1.20 (0.65–2.21)	0.56
		<i>Eimeria spp.</i>	1.65 (0.82–3.30)	0.16
Sex	Male (n=132) vs. Female (n=113)	<i>Balantidium spp.</i>	0.95 (0.50–1.81)	0.88
		<i>Eimeria spp.</i>	1.30 (0.66–2.56)	0.45
Age	Per year (continuous)	<i>Balantidium spp.</i>	0.97 (0.88–1.07)	0.55

Risk Factor	Category	Name of the Parasite Identified	Odds Ratio (95% CI)	p-value
		<i>Eimeria spp.</i>	0.92 (0.83–1.02)	0.11

In our research, no statistically significant associations were observed between *Eimeria* spp. infections and breed, sex, or age (**Tables 4**). Crossbreed cattle exhibited 1.65 times higher odds of infection compared to local breeds, though this trend lacked significance. Males showed marginally higher odds than females, while each additional year of age corresponded to an 8% non-significant reduction in infection odds.

CHAPTER 5 DISCUSSION

The present study identified a 29.8% prevalence of *Paramphistomum spp.* infection among cattle in the Barishal District, reflecting a substantial parasitic burden. This finding aligns with the results of Paul *et al.* (2011), who reported a higher prevalence of 53.1% in cattle from Sirajganj district. The discrepancy in prevalence may be attributed to regional differences in climate, pasture management, snail population density (as intermediate hosts), and seasonal sampling. Despite the variation in infection rates, both studies underscore the endemicity of *Paramphistomum spp.* in Bangladesh. This variation may be due to a higher density of intermediate snail hosts, such as *Planorbis* species, that are crucial for the parasite's life cycle. Additionally, regional differences in climate and pasture management practices could contribute to varying levels of exposure to *Paramphistomum* larvae (Maitra *et al.*, 2014).

Fasciola spp. infections were observed in 20.0% of the cattle, with age identified as a statistically significant risk factor. Each additional year of age increased the odds of infection by 8%, indicating cumulative exposure over time. The significant association between age and *Fasciola* spp. infection observed in this study aligns with findings from various regions. In Shahjampur, Sirajganj, Karim *et al.* (2015) reported a higher prevalence of fasciolosis in older cattle, with infection rates increasing from 48.62% in cattle under 3 years to 76.43% in those over 5 years. Similarly, a study in Bauphal Upazila, found that cattle older than 5 years had a prevalence rate of 71.43%, compared to 47.06% in those under 3 years. (Karim *et al.*, 2015). The higher prevalence of *Fasciola* spp. in older cattle observed in this study can be attributed to cumulative exposure over time, as these animals have spent more years grazing in contaminated pastures. The prolonged exposure to infected water bodies and snails, the intermediate hosts of *Fasciola* spp., likely increases the likelihood of infection in these animals.

The lack of significant associations between *Fasciola* spp. infection and breed or sex, consistent with Rahman *et al.* (2017), suggests that environmental and management factors, such as grazing practices and access to contaminated water, are more critical in controlling fascioliasis.

The observed prevalence of *Balantidium* spp. infections in cattle in this study (13.9%) is notably lower than the 54.7% reported by Paul *et al.* (2019) in Mymensingh district, Bangladesh. This may be attributed to differences in study methodologies, sample sizes, and regional environmental

factors. On the other hand, *Eimeria spp.* infections were identified in 11.8% of the cattle sampled in this study. While this prevalence is moderate, it is important to note that *Eimeria* infections can lead to significant economic losses due to decreased productivity. For instance, *Eimeria zuernii*, one of the most pathogenic species, can cause illness in 10–80% of animals and reduce gross margins by 8–9%, leading to estimated annual losses of \$731 million globally (Sarfaraz *et al.*, 2025). The study did not find significant associations between *Eimeria spp.* infection and factors such as breed, sex, or age, suggesting that environmental and management factors may play more critical roles in infection risk. Previous research has indicated that factors such as high stocking density, accumulation of fecal material, and suboptimal hygiene practices can increase the risk of *Eimeria* infections. (Campbell, 2021).

Ascaris spp. infections were found in 10.2% of cattle, consistent with other studies in Bangladesh, such as Azam *et al.* (2017), who reported a 2.44% prevalence in Joypurhat Sadar Upazila, highlighting regional variability.

The absence of significant associations between *Ascaris spp.* infection and factors such as breed, sex, or age in this study suggests that environmental factors may play a more substantial role in infection risk. Environmental contamination, particularly through pasture and water sources, is a known contributor to *Ascaris* transmission (Sayeed *et al.*, 2024)

In this study, *Strongyloides spp.* infections were found in 5.7% of fecal samples of cattle. A study conducted in Ullapara Upazila, Bangladesh, reported a higher prevalence of *Strongyloides spp.* (16.53%) in cattle aged between 1 to 2 years, with a general prevalence of 45.46% for strongyle eggs across all age groups (Akter *et al.*, 2023). This indicates that while regional differences exist, *Strongyloides spp.* remains a significant concern in Bangladesh. The variability in prevalence rates between studies may be attributed to differences in environmental conditions, grazing practices, and management strategies across regions (Sejuti *et al.*, 2021).

In the present study, *Schistosoma spp.* infections were detected in 3.7% of the cattle population. This prevalence is notably lower than the 47.5% reported by Islam *et al.* (2011) in Mymensingh, Bangladesh. The disparity may be due to differences in ecological settings, sampling periods, or management practices. Unlike our findings, Islam *et al.* (2011) observed significant associations between infection rates and factors such as age, sex, and rearing system, with older, male, and semi-intensively reared cattle showing higher prevalence. This contrast highlights the influence of

local environmental conditions and husbandry systems on infection risk, emphasizing the need for region-specific control strategies.

CHAPTER 6

CONCLUSION

This study highlights a critical burden of gastrointestinal (GI) parasitic infections in cattle in Barishal District, with a prevalence of 100%. Trematodes particularly *Paramphistomum spp.* and *Fasciola spp.* were most prevalent. Protozoa and nematodes further indicate diverse parasitic threats with both health and zoonotic implications.

Most infections showed no significant association with cattle demographics, suggesting widespread exposure due to communal grazing and inadequate parasite control. An exception was *Fasciola spp.*, where risk increased with age, likely reflecting cumulative exposure.

Zoonotic parasites such as *Balantidium spp.* and *Schistosoma spp.* pose public health concerns, particularly in areas with poor sanitation and water quality. The overall high parasitic burden in cattle implies substantial economic losses from reduced productivity.

Effective control requires integrated strategies, including targeted deworming, snail control, improved pasture management, and farmer education. Government, non-government organizations as well as the Department of Livestock Services (DLS) must enhance surveillance and access to deworming programs. Future research should be attempted on seasonal trends, economic impacts, and species diversity using molecular tools. A coordinated One Health approach is essential for sustainable control of GI parasitism in cattle.

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